

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ULTRA-HIGH STRENGTH WIRES BY THE DEFORMATION OF IN-SITU COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In-situ composites such as Cu-Nb and Cu-Ag can be deformed by wire drawing to produce wires with strength levels of the order of 1 to 1.5 GPa. It is unlikely that a single strengthening mechanism is operative over the total strain range (ϵ up to 10) needed to develop this strength. Thus, a variety of techniques have been utilized to investigate the structural changes occurring in these wires during processing. Attention has been given to the detailed morphological evolution of the second phase during processing and this yields new insights into the ways in which co-deformation leads to materials with strength levels close to the theoretical strength.

INTRODUCTION

The observations of ultra-high mechanical strength obtained after extensive deformation of in-situ composites have been the subject of numerous recent studies [e.g. 1,2,3]. These studies have given rise to a variety of models to predict the evolution of strength as a function of imposed strain or the microstructural scale of the composite. In this paper, we examine these models in light of the detailed experimental evidence relating to the scale and morphology of the second phase. In addition, the requirements of the manufacturing processes involved are discussed.

Before examining the details of various models, it is instructive to first consider some fundamental aspects of the behaviour of two-phase materials. The data of Frommeyer and Wassermann [4] is replotted in Fig. 1, and is typical of the general behaviour of most fine-scale, two-phase systems and their bulk constituents after deformation. The pure materials reach a point at which additional cold work no longer produces increased strength. In the simplest terms, this saturation indicates that the rate of hardening is equal to the rate of recovery.

In the eutectic alloy, however, there is no indication of reaching a saturation stress up to strains of the order of 10. There are two possible explanations for this behaviour. The first possibility is that the second phase stabilizes the matrix microstructure and prevents recovery from occurring. The second possibility is that the second phase introduces an additional work hardening term (or terms) such that the overall work hardening rate exceeds the rate of recovery in the matrix alone. The remainder of this paper will deal with the implications of these two scenarios.

In order to investigate the processes at work in these two-phase systems, it is worthwhile to first make some additional, general observations:

Figure 1. The data of Frommeyer and Wassermann for drawn copper, silver, and the copper-silver eutectic.

- High strength has been attained in a number of two-phase systems whose components have widely varying bulk properties. viz. Cu-Nb, Cu-Ag, Fe-Fe₃C.
- The generation of the highest strength levels comes after extensive deformation, typically by wire drawing or rolling, which reduces the scale of both phases (i.e. the second phase co-deforms with the matrix).
- The ultimate strength, and presumably also the yield strength of the two-phase materials is inversely proportional to the interphase spacing although the value of the exponent (i.e. λ^{-1} , $\lambda^{-1/2}$) is in question.

COMMENTS ON STABILITY (INHIBITING RECOVERY)

With respect to the process of work hardening, there are two aspects of stability which are of importance. The first is the morphological stability of the microstructure and the second concerns the stability of the dislocation substructure in the material. The work of Hong et al. [5] on the copper-silver and copper-niobium systems demonstrated that the fine, filamentary structure of these materials was stable up to temperatures of the order of 200°C. At higher temperatures, spheroidization and/or reprecipitation of the second phase occurred.

The nature of the dislocation substructure in these heavily deformed materials has been the subject of some debate and various attempts have been made to measure the dislocation densities [2, 3, 4, 6]. At this point, however, it is not necessary to have precise numbers for the dislocation densities. It is sufficient to note the consistent TEM observation that after large deformations, significant concentrations of dislocations are only found in areas which are free from the second phase. This suggests that, if dislocations are being stored in the two-phase regions, they must be in the interface between the matrix and second phase.

To all levels of strain reported in the literature for the Cu-X systems, the work hardening rate does not fall to zero. (i.e. the deformed microstructure is sufficiently resistant to recovery to allow the continued storage of energy). This continued hardening must reach a limit as the theoretical strength is approached. However, it has most likely been the practical limit of dealing with increasingly finer wires which has prevented this upper limit of strength from being reached. (The 1.4 GPa wire of Frommeyer and Wassermann in Fig. 1 was 100 μm in diameter.)

Figure 2. Schematic work hardening behaviour for a pure material and a two-phase alloy.

The typical work hardening behaviour of a pure metal like polycrystalline copper is shown schematically by the solid line in Fig. 2. The typical behaviour consists of an initially high rate of work hardening, followed by a progressive decrease to a lower, constant rate (Stage IV) and finally, the saturation stress is reached and the work hardening rate falls to zero. If the role of the second phase was solely that of a microstructural stabilizer, then it would be expected that the strength of a two-phase material like copper-silver would be due solely to the extended Stage IV hardening shown by the dashed line in Fig. 2. In fact, the apparent work hardening rate estimated from the UTS vs. strain data of Frommeyer and Wassermann in Fig. 1 is of the same order as the typical Stage IV hardening rate reported for polycrystalline copper [7] ($\theta_{CuAg} \approx 110$ MPa, $\theta_{Cu} \approx 80$ MPa).

While the hardening rates of the pure matrix and two-phase alloys are similar, there is currently no conclusive evidence to support or refute either of the scenarios proposed in the Introduction. The lack of significant dislocation densities observed in the matrix suggests that it is not likely that the continued strengthening is due solely to the conventional work hardening of the matrix. There must, in fact, be one or more additional storage mechanisms due to the two-phase nature of the material.

COMMENTS ON HARDENING MECHANISMS

If the inhibition of recovery (or more appropriately, if conventional work hardening of the matrix) is not sufficient to explain the increased strength in these materials, it becomes necessary to postulate additional energy storage mechanisms to account for the continued work hardening. In previous studies of these materials, three modeling approaches have been prevalent:

1. The first is essentially a continuum approach employing a rule-of-mixtures formulation. [2]. This approach can also be modified to account for the interactions between the two phases which allows the bulk properties to evolve as the scale of the microstructure evolves. [8, 9]
2. The second considers substructural hardening by the generation of geometrically necessary dislocations due to incompatible flow of the matrix and second phase [3].
3. The third approach proposes a Hall-Petch type barrier strengthening model based on the interphase spacing[1].

The first point that must be considered before choosing a model is the form of the data itself. Particularly in the investigations of the Cu-X systems, the strength data has invariably been reported as UTS versus strain or average interphase spacing. The concern is that the modeling approaches listed above (particularly 2 and 3) are based on predicting the flow stress of the material. Fig. 3 shows a typical stress-strain curve from a tensile test of a Cu-18wt%Nb wire. The ultimate stress

Figure 3. Experimental engineering stress - true strain curve for a drawn Cu-18wt%Nb wire.

is greater than 1200 MPa, however, the initial departure from elastic behaviour occurs at approximately 450 MPa and the 0.2% offset yield point is 790 MPa. This complicated yielding behaviour is difficult to handle from a modeling perspective and indicates that the onset of plastic flow is not homogeneous over the cross-section of the material.

All of the modeling approaches listed above have been shown to fit the presented data. However, there has yet to be any conclusive evidence to resolve the details of any of the models. In the discussion, we will present some experimental observations which relate to the applicability of the various modeling approaches with a view to determining which strengthening mechanisms are likely to be operative in these high strength materials.

DISCUSSION

The absence of high observed dislocation densities indicates that the continued work hardening of the two-phase materials is not due to the continuation of conventional Stage IV work hardening of the matrix or the generation of geometrically necessary dislocations. Because of this, it is necessary to postulate additional mechanisms of energy storage.

The pronounced rounding of the yield point and Bauschinger loops on unloading and reloading shown in Fig. 3 are typical of materials which are supporting large elastic stresses. A very simple experiment on the copper-niobium system has shown this to be qualitatively true. Fig. 4a) is an SEM micrograph of niobium filaments extracted from a wire which had been drawn to a total strain of 5. Fig. 4b) shows filaments extracted after the wire had been exposed to 500°C for one hour. The as-drawn filaments in Fig. 4a) show pronounced curvature indicating the presence of residual stress prior to extraction. The filaments extracted after annealing are straight, and in some instances have begun to spheroidize. A crude estimate may be made of the magnitude of the residual stress in the filaments by measuring the thickness and radius of curvature of the exposed filaments and applying simple beam theory. For the filaments shown in Fig. 4a), the estimated stress is of the order of $E/50$. (i.e. at or approaching the theoretical strength of the material.)

It is interesting to consider the origin of these elastic stresses.. In materials which contain a hard second phase, (e.g. SiC reinforced aluminum) residual stresses are generated on unloading after the matrix has deformed plastically while the second phase remains elastic. Fig. 5a) and b) are micrographs of the same niobium wire embedded in a copper matrix in the as-cast and drawn

a)

b)

Figure 4. Niobium filaments extracted from a Cu-Nb wire in the a) as-drawn condition and b) after annealing at 500°C for one hour prior to extraction.

($\epsilon=2.75$) condition. Although there is a change in the cross-sectional shape[10], image analysis on six similar wires reveals the average reduction in area to be equal to the overall strain in the wire. This result shows quantitatively that the niobium co-deforms with the copper matrix and, therefore, must be sheared by matrix dislocations.

In the case of a dislocation passing from one phase to another, it is most likely that the Burger's vectors in each phase will not be equal. The process of shearing the second phase will, therefore, leave residual misfit dislocations at the interface between the two phases. An excellent illustration of this is in the high resolution TEM work of Guétaz and Pénisson on a two-phase Ni-Co superalloy[11]. Argon and Haasen [12] have proposed a similar mechanism of glide dislocations cutting cell walls to account for the Stage IV hardening of single phase metals. For each glide dislocation that cuts a second phase filament, an additional strain equal to the difference in axial components of the matrix and second phase Burger's vectors is introduced and elastic strain energy is stored. However, the filaments shown in Fig. 2a) were examined after being drawn to a strain of 5. At this point they already appear to be supporting stresses at or close to the theoretical limit. Therefore, while the storage of elastic strain energy will contribute to the work hardening rate, it is not likely that it is solely responsible for the work hardening up to $\epsilon=10$.

In view of the observations of large elastic stresses in the niobium filaments and the attempts to model the strength of these materials via a continuum approach, it is worthwhile to examine the implications of considering the second phase to be a theoretically strong reinforcement in a metal matrix. If, for example, we choose a Cu-20%Nb composite with $\sigma_{Nb} = E/50 \approx 2$ GPa, a rule-of-mixtures calculation predicts that to reach composite strength of 1 GPa, the strength of the copper matrix would have to be 750 MPa. This is approaching twice the strength of drawn copper. Clearly there must be an additional contribution to the strengthening of the composite.

There is another contribution to the hardening of the composite to consider as a result of the co-deformation of the two phases. As the two phases continue to co-deform, there is necessarily an increase in the ratio of interface surface to second phase volume. Increasing internal surface area requires energy and will increase the flow stress by an amount given by[7]:

$$\sigma^{int} = \frac{d(SA/V)}{d\epsilon} \gamma \quad (1)$$

Figure 5. A niobium wire embedded in a copper matrix in the a) as-cast, and b) drawn ($\epsilon=2.75$) condition. The reduction in area of the niobium wire equals the overall reduction of the composite.

assuming the the surface energy, γ , does not vary with strain. If the second phase is assumed to be cylindrical and deforms to the same strain as the total wire, the Equation (1) becomes:

$$\sigma^{\text{int}} = \left(\frac{-2}{l_0 \exp(\epsilon/2)} + \frac{2 \exp(\epsilon/2)}{d_0} \right) \gamma \quad (2)$$

The first term quickly becomes negligible and the equation reduces to:

$$\sigma^{\text{int}} = \frac{2\gamma}{d_0} \exp(\epsilon/2) \quad (3)$$

The contribution to the work hardening rate may also be calculated:

$$\theta^{\text{int}} = \frac{d\sigma^{\text{int}}}{d\epsilon} = \frac{\gamma}{d_0} \exp(\epsilon/2) \quad (4)$$

Care must be taken in employing Equations (3) and (4) to maintain a physical basis for the calculations. At first glance, it would appear that, with sufficient strain, very large strengths are attainable due to the exponential dependence. However, microstructural stability will set a lower limit to the filament size, $d_1 = \exp(\epsilon/2)/d_0$.

It is still instructive to apply numbers to Equations (3) and (4) to explore the limits of this mechanism. If a value of 0.5 J/m^2 is chosen for the interface surface energy and a lower limit for the filament size is set at 5 nm, then the potential increase in strength due to the creation of internal surface is 200 MPa and the instantaneous contribution to the hardening rate is 100 MPa. This hardening rate is of the same order as that estimated earlier from the data of Frommeyer and Wassermann.

ASPECTS OF DEFORMATION

There are a number of aspects of the deformation of two-phase materials that warrant consideration here and lend insight into the operative strengthening mechanisms in these materials. To that end,

Figure 6. An atomic force microscopy image of a niobium filament extracted after drawing to a strain of 5. The horizontal lines on the image are a function of the imaging technique.

it is again useful to comment on a few general observations.

In general, the second phase in the as-cast material is randomly oriented with respect to the deformation axis. As the deformation proceeds, the second phase aligns with the wire axis and the interphase spacing decreases. Simple geometric arguments can be used to show that the average slip line length will decrease more rapidly during the alignment process than during the subsequent deformation of the aligned structure [13]. Because the strength of the material is related to this interphase spacing, the range of strain over which the microstructure is being aligned will have a higher work hardening rate than the subsequent refinement stage.

At high strains ($\epsilon > 5$), the second phase filaments attain thicknesses of the order of 10–50 nm. At these dimensions, virtually any strain localization would be sufficient to shear through the second phase. The constraint provided by the wire drawing process, however, ensures that the deformation is very homogeneous. Fig. 6 is an atomic force microscopy image of the broad face of an extracted niobium filament. The diagonal striations develop after strains of the order of 4 and remain present up to the highest strains. The striations make a consistent angle of between 55–57° with the filament axis. This filament is roughly 25 nm thick and the height of the striations is 3–5 nm. It is an interesting observation that these striations do not correspond to traces from any rational slip plane in the bcc niobium. They do, however, correspond to traces of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ slip plane in the copper and may indicate that the niobium is forced to conform to the deformation in the copper matrix.

CONCLUSIONS

To explain the continued strengthening of heavily-drawn, two-phase materials, it is essential to uncover the mechanism of energy storage. TEM observations by all investigators have shown that the conventional storage of dislocations is not able to account for the sustained work hardening. While conclusive evidence in the Cu-X systems is not yet available, the generation of residual elastic strain in the filaments, dislocation debris from incompatible Burger's vectors, and the increase in internal surface area appear to be probable mechanisms for this energy storage and suggest estimates for the work hardening rate that are of the correct order.

At present, there is direct evidence that the interfacial area in the composites increases with increasing strain, as well as quantitative evidence of the elastic stresses borne by niobium filaments. What is required to clarify this subject is direct evidence of the presence of interfacial misfit dislocations as in the Ni-Co system [11], but perhaps more difficult will be to understand the energy associated with an interface under the large tractions present in these materials.

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